

SOCIAL ANALYSIS OF INFORMATION EXCHANGE CULTURE

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It is characteristic that in the works on the theory of the press, and in the statements of sociologists-practitioners on the pages of professional periodicals, the mentioned requirement of combining sociology and social psychology is increasingly interpreted with reference to the study of the information fabric of the sociology of activity, to the sphere of information exchange (communication, interaction) of people.

Among the theories, contiguous sociology of interaction, it is necessary to name the "theory of communication" (Mansurov V.A, Mansurov N.S, Nozhin E.A, Fedyakina I.A, etc. participated in its development); "Information theory" (also known as the "theory of awareness"), about the necessity of which was written by Gott V.S. and Ursul A.D.; "The theory of social information," one of the authors of which is Afanasyev V.G.;

Formation of sociology of communication was facilitated and is being facilitated by many attempts at analytical penetration into the sphere of communication - both from the side of philosophers and sociologists (the works of Afanasiev V.G, Grushin B.A, Bueva L.P, Zhuravlev G.T, Kagan M.S, Korobeinikov V.S, Sokovnin V.M), and psychologists (the works of Agaltsev A.M, Zlobina E.G, Kolominsky Y.L, Leontiev A.A, Lomov B.F, Parygin B.D, Sherkovina A.A. and others).

Since the object of our study is interaction of people, it is as unlimited in life and diverse as human society itself. The diversity in its own way was reflected in social science. In the literature on philosophy, psychology, and the theory of the press itself do we count dozens of definitions of the notion of "communication", which are very different in both meaning and scope. Our task is not to classify and examine the whole variety of definitions, especially since they reflect such aspects of the content and functions of communication as the exchange of activities, abilities, feelings, emotional states, etc.

So, communication is mostly the exchange of information. This definition distinguishes also from the very concept of "communication", and from that environment, or those processes that it reflects (i.e. from information sphere and processes), the most essential component of them.

Firstly, the "world of communication" that is familiar to it is just a small fragment of the real world of people's communication.

Secondly, the professional employee of the press, radio, television usually knows neither the laws of this "big world", nor the driving forces, nor many other important features of it, even though these laws, forces and features have a broad social scale than one that is commensurate with the scope of the journalist's profession, and because its laws have not been sufficiently studied by science.

Communication in its integral social scope and significance is studied by a complex of social science sciences, and first of all by sociology. Therefore, it is interesting to at least be acquainted with the facts and conclusions collected and made by social scientists regarding the communication of people in society.

As already noted, communication is a phenomenon that is primarily of an informational nature. This is a special kind of information process. In general, information processes which is transmission, reception, selection, storage, etc. in the scales of society appear as a movement, the circulation of messages, knowledge, etc., or how the dissemination of information to provide it with various social processes, including the processes of social organization and management. Information processes cover the entire social organism, permeate all social subsystems, they are available in any level, even the smallest fragment of public life.

Information process is clothed not always in the form of a word, language, and writing. On the contrary, there is reason to assert that the message in verbal (verbatim) form is only a relatively small and special part of information exchange in the society.

"Information that stimulates communication is as necessary as food and heat, not only as the presence of energy fields in which all vital activities of people on our planet happens," Academician Berg A.L writes.

Let's try to outline at least a general contour of the "information field" of the society, meaning that we will also denote the boundaries of communication. If we take as a basis the existing attempts at scientific systematization of social information, then we can draw conclusions, it can be individual (personal experience) and supra-individual; biological (genetic), hereditary and actually social, acquired; fixed and non-fixed in sign systems; predictive, planned, indicative, and so on².

Without going further into these varieties, we only note that all the diversity of information gives grounds to talk about such large areas of exchange

in the process of communication, such as communication a) in the field of material and spiritual production, b) in the processes of knowledge and dissemination of knowledge, that is, the sphere of social consciousness, c) in the processes of social organization and management, d) in the world of science and technology, e) in communication systems, f) in every human community, g) in the work community, h) in various social groups, i) in the family, finally, j) in the process of auto communication, that is, human communication with oneself.

As we can see, among these basic types of social information and, accordingly, the varieties of communication as an exchange of information. Deep social determination of people's communication raises the question of what is the role of this exchange of information for the life and development of society as a whole.

The traditional and widespread understanding among journalists of this issue, is usually based on self-evidence of "common sense" (people communicate because they are interested in it, because they know each other, the world, because, finally, that they are many and they have to live together and coordinate their actions, etc.), is already insufficient for sociology. And in order to overcome this "barrier of evidence", it is necessary to approach communication from the socio-philosophical point of view.

Similar view of information exchange is quite widespread in the scientific literature (for example, on monographs of Afanasyev V.G, Tyukhtin V.S, Ursula A.D, and others), and the characteristic for it is precisely the translation of the entire research at a certain stage of it into the layer of the system (structural-functional) analysis.

Let's define the original concepts such as "information" and "information exchange." What is the information? It is a message, news, data. But for the sociophilosophical understanding of the entire mechanism of information exchange in a society, this (especially scientific or even practical-applied) treatment of "information" is not enough. And although in the following chapters we will return to this "narrow" understanding of the notion of "information", but now we need to rise above it, abstract from the features and particulars of "messages" in order to see features common to all types of information, to understand the typical in any process of information exchange, so that through the phenomenon or form of the beginning of this process, as Hegel said, to light on its essence.

Essence of information is not in the signs of the message, but in the fact that it is related to the level, degree of organization of the participants in the

information exchange. And the very exchange of information in its most general form is caused by the diversity of the organization of its participants, the differences in the orderliness of their structures, if these participants are also represented as generalized as possible: as systems.

Characteristics of the information exchange process:

1. Information exchange, no matter how important and independent it may seem in itself, always acts only as an official mechanism of interaction.

2. The most important final, in-depth result and the consequence of the functioning of the information mechanism is a mutually conditioned change in the organizational parameters of the participants in the interaction, their alignment, and their co-organization. In this sense, we can talk about the information management mechanism.

3. These and other features allow us to talk about the regulative function of information exchange (and communication, in particular) as the main one, ie, one to which any other of its functions can always be reduced (for example, the educational function of communication is a purposeful regulation of the formation consciousness, knowledge, worldview).

4. The exchange of information is directly related to the actualization of the relationship. Relationships are a condition and a sign of interaction. But in the sphere of information exchange they find their own special expression, for example, in the division of information into "potential" (possible, albeit objectively available) and "topical" (used).

5. The exchange of information is indicative. This means that, having data on at least one component of the interaction, we can confidently talk about the rest, we can calculate where and how to find them.

So, the analysis of concepts of "information" and "information exchange" gave the most general idea of the characteristic features of the process of information exchange and its connection with interaction, reflection, (co) organization, the idea of a "mechanism" role of information exchange in the life of society.

The world is rapidly developing. Today's novelty in science until managing to be yet released all over the world, the more advanced version of that same invention is appearing. This, of course, can be attributed to the participation of modern information technologies in information exchange. The reason is that only seconds are needed to send information from one place to another through the global network.

The features of socializing in the modern lifestyle of young people will depend on transformation of society and subjective situations that it has created. The task of young people in this process, the issues of forming the culture of information exchange in the information society, adaptation to the conditions and the prospects for future development should be scientifically analyzed and predicted in sociological terms.

In today's age of information, the policy of our state towards young generation is of great importance as the expression of the centuries-old aspirations of the nation's children in the education of the nation, the foundation of which is the noble goal of bringing up a healthy and harmoniously developed generation. Today's analysis of the world's strategy shows that there is a strong competition in the highly-informed societies. Dangers faced by the population, especially young people, are gaining momentum. Therefore, in the age of information, it is important to study the issues of forming and strengthening the worldview of young people on a scientific basis, to make the necessary conclusions, as well as to develop necessary methodological and practical recommendations.

For full resolution of the problem of youth, it is necessary to study comprehensively and thoroughly through the methods of sociological subjects. At the same time, for the benefit of the youth, this process should not be one-time, but repeated all the time. To do this, it is necessary to gradually monitor the thoughts and actions of young people.

Shavkat M. Mirziyoyev, The President of Uzbekistan made a speech at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly: "The young people of today's world are the largest generation in the history of human life amounting to 2 billion people. In this regard, the most important task is the struggle for the minds of people, for the minds of the youth. The next day, the welfare of the planet, depends on what kind of people these children will grow up. Our key task is to provide conditions for self-adjustment of the youth to create a barrier to the spread of the "virus" of ideology of the population. "

It is impossible to draw conclusions based on the results of a single study of the actual situation in the culture of information exchange among the Uzbek youth and the level of information culture, so it is vital to gradually phase out the problem of youth, develop effective ways and means of solving the problem.

The following recommendations have been developed as a result of this research:

creating a methodology for shaping the worldview for information among young people;

developing and disseminating information literacy guidelines to enhance the intellectual capacity of young people;

strengthening spiritual work in raising the spiritual image of youth in the era of globalization;

consistent implementation of measures to increase the culture of information exchange;

increasing normative documents on Internet Protocols when information is being exchanged in an informed society;

promoting the dissemination of scientific worldwide information resources in the rational use of young people's information resources.

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